

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The current thesis titled “Tourism Education in India: Perception of Academicians and Industry Professionals” entirely centers on the present scenario and dynamics of Tourism Education in India. The thesis has reviewed myriad of journals, studies and newspapers on the present condition and outlook of the various stakeholders towards this sector. The wide success of any sector, discipline or department depends on the student learning outcomes on the one hand and their adjustment as professionals in this perspective is on the other. The present study, after reviewing literature on the respective area, has planned to study the contemporary attitude of the two main vehicles of tourism sector- attitude of the academicians who are responsible to give a new magnitude to the sector and the attitude of Industrial Professionals who seek to utilize the human capital in the respective industry. Thus there is a great need to frame an equilibrium between the creator of tourism professionals, like colleges and universities, and the takers of professionals i.e. the respective industries.

6.1 Conclusion

The conclusions of the research are discussed under various subheadings

a) **Tourism Programs being offered in India**

- Tourism Programs being offered by various public Universities / Institutions across the country are not under a particular Department or Faculty. While Tourism Department is a separate entity in some organizations, others offer the program under different departments like Management, History or Geography and also under different Faculty.
- In the Institutions where tourism is an independent discipline/department, it is performing better than functioning under other departments.
- There is a marked difference in the nomenclature being used for tourism programs offered at various universities. While some call it Tourism, others have clubbed it with Hospitality. Some Universities call it a Management program and other name it as an Administration degree.
- There is difference in the duration of Tourism Degree courses being offered by various public Universities.

b) **Tourism Course Curriculum**

- Some degree of similarity is found in the course curriculum being offered under the Tourism Programs offered by various Universities.

- Largely the curriculum for tourism programs at various Universities is developed by input of Internal Faculty, Faculty members of other Universities and Industry Professionals. However, the most desired approach for curriculum development by tourism academicians and industry professionals comprises members from government, academicians from Tourism Education Institute, industry professionals from Tourism Industry and office bearers of Tourism Board
- The tourism professionals conclude that areas to be improved in curriculum are Frequent syllabus Update (FSU), Industry Interaction (II), Job Training (JT), Research (Res.), Tourism Software (TS), Digital Skills (DS), Academia-Industry Network (AIN) and Student Exchange Programs (SEP).
- Majority of tourism education institutes do not provide tourism software training in concerned departments.
- The components of sustainable development and international peace are not included in most tourism programs.
- The tourism professionals have kept frequent syllabus updates on priority to bridge the gap between produced human resource and industry requirements.
- The study found that Foreign Language Skills, Tourism Software Skills, Outdoor Skills, Research skills, Presentation skills, Digital skills, Marketing Skills and Tourism Industry Ethics (TIES) are below the expectations of tourism industry requirements.
- The academicians are of the view that Confidence Level, Outdoor Skills, Presentation Skills, Tourism Industry Ethics Skills and Travel Ethics Skills are top five areas in which students are being oriented through tourism programs.

c) Professional produced by Tourism Education Organizations

- Majority employees in the tourism industry are from other educational backgrounds and less than fifty percent employed are from tourism education backgrounds.
- The majority of industry professionals rated the newly produced tourism graduates as moderate or low category. The reasons cited for this are less ability in foreign languages, lack of travel software knowledge, poor orientation in outdoor activities, poor in research, presentation and digital skills and less travel ethics.
- It was found that travel companies' requirements are focused on specialization based tourism services while tourism education institutions are providing general tourism education.

- The Industry professionals rated Accommodation, Destination Management, Tour Operation, MIS and Event Management as top five subjects in which high skills and specialization is required

d) Tourism Academics and Industry Interaction

- The majority of tourism academicians and industrial professionals are of the opinion that, to deliver ideal tourism education/to produce ideal tourism professionals in the country, there is a high need of improvement and incorporation of Industry-Interaction, Job Training, Academia-Industry Network and Student Exchange Programs.

6.2) Recommendations

On the bases of conclusion the following recommendations are provided under the following heads

a) Basic Reforms for Tourism Education Quality Enhancement

- All the Public Universities offering tourism programs should establish an ‘independent tourism department’, with strengthened infrastructure and able faculty. Every department should have a ‘departmental library’ with enhanced tourism literature, a ‘placement cell’ with exemplary network with tourism service providers, technically equipped ‘tourism software training labs’, and a ‘student support cell’ to nourish the competencies of students and provide and exposure to the travel trade world.
- There is need to motivate the academicians to tap their utmost potential with regards to networking, academic and research experience as well as continuously orient them in new skills that they can impart the same to the students as is desired by the industry.
- Tourism education should be incorporated in elementary education through schools of the country.
- There is dire need to establish a ‘National Tourism University’ for tourism education, to develop standardized curriculum, specialisation based tourism education programs, a portal of public tourism education institutes exist in the country, uniformity in departments under which tourism education is being offered. There should also be provision to strengthen the existing physical and human resource infrastructure in institutes

- Conduct of a Common Admission Test (CAT) for tourism is also recommended for intake of quality and deserving students in tourism studies.
- Quality assessment of tourism academicians and of tourism education being delivered should be carried out by a National body on regular intervals in order to maintain Quality.

b) Course Curriculum Development

- There is a pressing need for active and regular industry participation in curriculum design of tourism programs to frame syllabus that meets the needs of the industry and orients the students in the required skills of the trade. Applicability of the knowledge in the trade should be at the core of framing curriculum.
- As the tourism industry comprises a vast number of composite sectors, it is desirable that the curriculum should include a component of 'specialization' (e.g. airline, accommodations, travel business, event management, MICE etc), so that after the basic required tourism education a student is geared in his areas of interest and specialisation which can also enable him/her to specific composite sector of the trade.
- Rigorous Internship program needs to be a part of the Curriculum for orienting and acclimatizing the students in the actual industry work.
- There is urgent need to enhance product development skills among tourism graduates.
- Active tourism research should also be promoted by Tourism Educational Institutions.

c) Academia-Industry Interaction

- Constant interaction between tourism education providers and industry professionals should be taken as the key to deliver required need-of-the-hour tourism education meet the specific demands of the industry.
- Regular interface between industry and tourism academicians should be promoted so that the professionals can contribute to enhancing the trade skills of the academicians which can be further extended to students.
- Collaboration needs to be promoted between academia and industry with regards to research and development.

- Networking among educational institutes, technocrats, private sectors and government should be encouraged to review tourism education in context of futuristic needs.
- Tourism education, training and employment through tourism, should be taken up at the center of economic development while framing national and international tourism policies.
- Tourism students and academics should work in collaboration with the industry to conduct joint tourism events like conferences, trade shows etc, that can facilitate more integration between the two and sharing of concepts, ideas and skills.

Lastly, the research recommends that setting up 'Indian Tourism Service' (ITS), (similar to that of Indian Administrative Services) that can attract talented tourism graduates in tourism planning. ITS can go a long way in paving the path for development of the tourism in the country in a proper and competitive manner.